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Sławomir Sztobryn

Memory. There are people who are not forgotten

Words of gratitude and deep respect for Maria Dmitrivna Kul'taeva from her colleague Sławomir Sztobryn.

I met Professor Maria Kul'taeva for the first time at the Congress of the Society for Philosophical Pedagogy in Warsaw in 2016. At that time, she came at my invitation with Professor Lyudmila Gorbunova. The fruit of this meeting was the signing of a document on cooperation between TPF (Towarzystwo pedagogiki filozoficznej – Polish Society of philosophical pedagogy) and the journal “Philosophy of Education”. During the breaks of the conference we had the opportunity to get to know each other better. Professor Kul'taeva impressed me with her cordial attitude and great intellectual culture. I was impressed by her immense knowledge of many areas of the humanities, as well as her incredible knowledge of Polish literary and scientific culture.

Later on, we had the opportunity to meet a few more times at the Conventions of the Society, of which, of course, she became a member. I think that following her example and under her guidance, many other scholars from Kharkiv and Kyiv wished to join in our now joint activities. A beautiful example of our collaboration was the Ukrainian 2015 issue of the journal *Philosophical Pedagogy Online* [Kul'taeva 2015]. By participating and publishing with TPF, Mrs. Professor also included the Polish community in the cooperation with “Philosophy of Education”. The last chord of our cooperation is the publication soon to be published *Culture and Upbringing in the Local and Global World, Bielsko-Biala 2023*.

Sometimes, while participating in conferences organized by the Professor, I sent my texts, which she brought to the Ukrainian reader in the national language. She always did it with great energy and incredible ease. We corresponded a lot with each other. Mrs. Maria, because that's what she allowed herself to be called, mentioned that she was taking care of her loved ones, that she was reading a lot in those years of horror (including Polish literature), that she was organizing scientific life in her city, but she never complained, never complained.

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She was a quiet heroine. She fought for the continuity of Ukrainian culture, for the dignity of science, for humanistic relations among people. I do not remember Mrs. Maria to be sad. She was always cheerful, smiling, full of natural cordiality, always engaging in interesting conversation. She quoted from memory many Polish authors and especially Cyprian Kamil Norwid, a favorite of hers and of mine.

Although she lived far away, she was very close to me. Her passing is a loss for me, it is a loss for the TPF community, it is a loss for science. Her endearing character will remain in our memories. Her work will remain a lasting contribution to the pedagogical culture of Ukraine and Poland.

We bid her farewell with sadness

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Славомир Штобрин. Пам'ять. Є люди, яких не забувають

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Stawomir Sztobryn, Doctor Habilitated in Pedagogy, Professor Extraordinarius, Institute of Pedagogy, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Bielsko-Biała University (Poland).

E-mail: s.sztobryn@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3439-9200>

Штобрин, Славомир, доктор педагогічних наук, екстраординарний професор, Інститут педагогіки факультету гуманітарних та соціальних наук, Бельсько-Бяльський університет (Польща).

E-mail: s.sztobryn@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3439-9200>